

Housing Session Report

by the chair, Miles Glendinning

The mass housing question: a European dilemma?

The Final Program for the 2000 lays special stress on the relationships between modern urban form and political meaning and urban social change. These relationships were seen at their most intense in the field of housing. However, that identity was chronologically and geographically restricted, being confined largely to mid 20th-century Europe. That very restrictedness, and the contrast with other parts of the world, is itself significant in the context of contemporary globalisation. Docomomo, with its twin focus on past and future and its global scope, is well placed to bring out these lessons.

Historical definition

In mid 20th-century Europe, housing was the building type which was seen as the key arena for actually realising on a large scale the MoMo's values of mass provision in accordance with rationalist standards. Interwar aspirations and prototypes were followed, after World War II, by huge efforts to implement modern mass housing production on a general basis. Inevitably, because of the highly politicised status of the 'housing question' in Europe, housing production also became bound up with politics. More precisely, it became bound up with a process of forceful advocacy followed by equally vehement rejection. Within Europe and Russia (European and Asian), alongside the common architectural forms (tower blocks, etc.), there were considerable differences in the way that interrelationship with politics was expressed. In the socialist bloc, mass housing was bound up with Soviet power and more extreme Fordist doctrines of mass production, while in Western Europe the social-democratic welfare state framework covered a broad spectrum, from direct state intervention (e.g. Scotland and England) to indirect subsidising of private production (Belgium). In all cases, that phase of forceful production was followed by a political-architectural rejection, which varied from the 1960s/70s reaction against state paternalism in W Europe to the post-1989 collapse of Soviet power in the 'east'. Overall, the trend was away from centralisation to more 'participatory' processes, and away from 'social planning' to more

'market' contexts. Bound up with these was a rich discourse of socio-political controversy, with terms such as 'democracy', 'equality' and 'human' used in radically differing contexts.

Little or none of these violent fluctuations were found in other parts of the world - with the exception of some dense city-states (e.g. Hong Kong) and exclaves of the socialist bloc (e.g. North Korea). Typical is the kind of pattern in Brasil, where (despite some set-piece projects) in general social housing had a far lower political profile, and the key setpieces of modern urbanism were of a more 'public' monumental character, including Brasilia as a whole. In such countries, individual private villas and private apartment blocks were more of a focus for Modernism - but inevitably at a lower level of prominence than the huge social projects in Europe. A special position was occupied by the USA, where some relatively large scale public housing programs were undertaken in the big cities, but at a severely restricted level of expense and cultural prestige, given the USA's orientation to market capitalism.

Documentation and preservation issues: facing the future

In the Housing Session at the 2000 Conference, the papers have been arranged to contrast the 'mass-housing European' and 'non-mass-housing, non-European' contexts, both in historical definition and in the implications for documentation and conservation. From the documentation/conservation viewpoint, the issue of social housing poses complex problems. In 'mass housing' countries, the extreme prominence, physical and historical, of the vast arrays of blocks and towers brings great advantages for documentation, both for the prestigious showpieces and for the 'everyday' areas. In both cases there is often copious archive material, ranging from newspaper and publicity reports to mundane municipal records and statistics. But this same prominence brings disadvantages and problems for preservation. The mass housing areas are often still highly contentious, and often the subjects of 'community' initiatives for invasive alterations or demolitions. In contrast to other Modernist programmes that were not targeted specifically at poorer people,

social housing, by its very nature and 'genuineness' inevitably has some self-stigmatising aspects, unless very carefully managed. In western and northern Europe, that stigmatising process forms part of the continuing wider decay of state welfarism. In the former socialist bloc countries, it is accentuated by the association of mass housing with Soviet oppression. In both cases, the late 1990s' revival of interest and fashionable status of Modernism has largely bypassed postwar mass social housing, which is often portrayed as a monstrous perversion of more poetic interwar Modernist ideals. Arguably, such a view is only possible by a credulous acceptance of the idealistic, emancipatory propaganda of the interwar 'pioneers', whereas in fact the large scale implementation of Modernist mass provision ideals was always inevitably bound to involve compromises and economies. To this writer, it seems clear that the huge and often now decaying social-housing zones of towers and slabs ringing cities across northern Europe, from Paris to Moscow, and even beyond towards Irkutsk and Khabarovsk, are part of the Modern Movement, a central and vital part, albeit a deeply problematic one. The same can be said, with even greater emphasis, of the vast and far more socially 'successful' social-housing programmes of Hongkong and Singapore. Outside Europe, the former USSR and these territories, 'housing' is far less of a distinct problem area for preservation, as the overwhelmingly private ownership of dwellings, whether in apartment blocks or single family houses, merges relatively seamlessly into the building stock as a whole: 'housing' is something far more fragmented and even individualised.

For future policy-makers in the field of urbanism, this strong contrast between the 'mass-housing' and 'non-mass-housing' parts of the world is highly instructive. It suggests the potential, but also the limits, of any resistance to the levelling-down, homogenising, fragmenting effects of present-day globalisation. The 'non-mass-housing' areas show the possibilities of working within the system of capitalism, making small-scale progress while the general built environment continues to develop anarchically. The 'mass-housing' areas show the possibilities of a heroic attempt to turn the tide, but also the risks of a heroic 'failure'. What

may come out of this comparison is the potential of a compromise between the two extremes: namely, interventions by the state which effectively harness and control the private sector, in accordance with large-scale urbanistic and habitation concepts, without attempting to build and manage mass housing itself.